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Contribution to the knowledge of Coleoptera of Albania: seven new records

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Key words: Coleoptera, *Pygopleurus*, *Oxythyrea*, *Sphenoptera*, *Meloe*, *Curculio*, new records, Albania.

Abstract. Seven Coleoptera species from 5 families are newly recorded from Albania, providing the first documented evidence of their occurrence in the country.

Introduction

The entomofauna of Albania currently remains among the least studied in Europe. It is evident that the numerous gaps in our knowledge of the country's insect fauna can be addressed only through systematic and comprehensive investigations. Nevertheless, given the present state of research, even isolated and fragmentary data are of substantial scientific value.

During an entomological expedition to Albania conducted from 3 to 23 May 2021 by A.I. Gubin (Donetsk), O.V. Pak (Donetsk), Yu.Ye. Skrylnyk (Kharkov) and I.G. Plyushch (Kiev), several beetle species previously unrecorded from Albania were discovered. Some of these findings were published earlier in a contribution devoted to longhorn beetles (Cerambycidae) (Lazarev & al., 2024). The present paper reports the first records of seven species of Coleoptera new for the fauna of Albania.

Material and methods

All materials were identified by the authors except *Sphenoptera (Deudora) gemmata gemmata* A.G. Olivier, 1790,

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which identified by its collector Yu. Skrylnyk.

Photos were taken by A.I. Gubin using Nikon D7200 camera with Nikon 105mm f/2.8G IF-ED AF-S VR Micro-Nikkor lens. Mounted specimens were photographed using Carl Zeiss Stemi 2000-C microscope with Zeiss AxioCam Erc 5s camera. Photos were stacked, improved for contrast and brightness using Adobe® Photoshop®CS5 and Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 2020 v9.2.1.10 software. Photo on fig. 9 was made by Yu.Ye. Skrylnyk using Canon EOS 6D camera with Canon EF-S 60mm f/2.8 Macro USM lens and C-AF 13mm extension tube.

Results

Family Glaphyridae Macleay, 1819

***Pygopleurus apicalis* (Brullé, 1832)**

Figs 1-2

Material examined. 12 exs., Albania, Gjirokaštër County, 1.6 km N Saraqinishtë vill., Lunxherise Mts., 40°07'08.07"N, 20°13'32.78"E, 916 m, 07-08.V.2021, A.I. Gubin leg.; 14 exs., the same data but I. Plyushch leg.; 5 exs., the same data but Yu. Skrylnyk leg.; 1 ex., Albania, Vlorë County, 17 km NNW Sarande, S env. of Lukove vill., 39°59'0.38"N, 19°54'47.61"E, 150 m, 06.V.2021, O. Pak leg.

Remarks. The species is known from Greece, North Macedonia, southwestern Bulgaria, and southern Serbia (Nikodým & Bezděk, 2016; Bollino et al., 2019; Byk et al., 2023). Examined specimens were collected in flowering meadows within open montane woodland (Fig. 2), where they were found inside the flowers of *Papaver* sp. (Fig. 1), together with another related species *Pygopleurus chrysonotus* (Brullé, 1832).

Family Scarabaeidae Latreille, 1802

***Oxythyrea dulcis* Reitter, 1899**

Figs 3-4

Material examined. 4 exs., Albania, Lezhë County, Lezhë distr., 6 km NW Shëngjin, Buna River-Velipoja Protected Landscape, 41°50'16.05"N, 19°31'52.70"E, 5 m, 13.V.2021, O. Pak leg.; 5 exs., the same data but Yu. Skrylnyk leg.; 17 exs., the same locality but

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22.V.2021, A.I. Gubin leg.; 11 exs., the same data but O. Pak leg.; 8 exs., the same data but Yu. Skrylnyk leg.

Remarks. The species is known from Greece, Montenegro and Turkey (Bezděk, 2016; Vondráček et al., 2018; Byk et al., 2022). Examined specimens were collected in coastal sand dunes (Fig. 4) on the inflorescences of *Cyperus capitatus* Vand. (Fig. 3).

Family Buprestidae Leach, 1815

Sphenoptera (Deudora) gemmata gemmata A.G. Olivier, 1790

Figs 9, 12

Material examined. 2 males, Albania, Vlorë County, 3.5 km E Vagalat, 39°45'43.02"N, 20°9'39.46"E, 81 m, 06.V.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. et det.

Remarks. According to Cobos (Cobos, 1986), the species is distributed in Southern Europe from Portugal and Spain to Former Yugoslavia, and in North Africa from Morocco to Egypt and Asia Minor. However, according to current data, the species is reliably known from Egypt, Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia, Spain, Portugal, Southern France, Italy (including Sicilia - as *Sphenoptera (D.) gemmata sicelidis* (Obenberger, 1916) and Croatia (Kalashian & Sakalian, 2007; Kalashian, 2016). The species' presence in other countries of the former Yugoslavia and in Greece requires confirmation. Examined specimens were collected in a plain covered with broom (*Genista* sp.) bushes (Fig. 12).

Sphenoptera (Deudora) signata Jakovlev, 1887

Figs 5-6

Material examined. 3 exs., Albania, Vlorë County, 7.5 km S Kaninë, Lungar Mts., 40°23'37.45"N, 19°31'10.09"E, 810 m, 16.V.2021, A.I. Gubin leg.; 1 ex., Albania, Gjirokaštër County, 8 km ENE Gjirokaštër, Saraqinisht vill. env., Lunxherise Mts., 40°06'51"N, 20°13'36"E, 830 m, 07.V.2021, O. Pak leg.

Remarks. The species is known from Bulgaria, North Macedonia, Greece, Turkey, Israel, Syria, Iran, Turkmenistan, Georgia, Armenia and Azerbaijan (Kalashian & Sakalian, 2007; Kalashian, 2016). Examined specimens were collected in mountain meadow (Fig. 6).

Figs 1-2. *Pygopleurus apicalis* (Brullé, 1832): 1 - couple on *Papaver* sp. flower, 2 - locality: Albania, Gjirokastër County, 1.6 km N Saraqinishtë vill., Lunxherise Mts., 40°07'08.07"N, 20°13'32.78"E, 916 m., 08.05.2021.

Figs 3-4. *Oxythyrea dulcis* Reitter, 1899: 3 - imago on *Cyperus capitatus* Vand. inflorescence, 4 - locality: Albania, Lezhë County, Lezhë distr., 6 km NW Shëngjin, Buna River-Velipoja Protected Landscape, 41°50'16.05"N, 19°31'52.70"E, 5 m., 22.05.2021.

Figs 5-6. *Sphenoptera (Deudora) signata* Jakovlev, 1887: 5 - imago, 6 - locality: Albania, Vlorë County, 7.5 km S Kaninë, Lungar Mts., 40°23'37.45"N, 19°31'10.09"E, 810 m., 16.05.2021.

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Family Meloidae Gyllenhal, 1810

***Meloe (Taphromeloe) erythrocnemus* Pallas, 1782**

Figs 7-8

Material examined. 1 ex., Albania, Vlorë County, 4.5 km S Kaninë, Lungar Mts., 40°23'57.34"N, 19°31'5.06"E, 757 m, 05.V.2021, A.I. Gubin leg.; 1 ex., the same data but Yu. Skrylnyk leg.; 1 ex., the same locality but 16.V.2021, I. Plyushch leg.

Remarks. The species is widely distributed from the Apennine Peninsula and North Africa to western China (Bologna, 2020). Examined specimens were collected in mountain meadow (Fig. 8).

Family Curculionidae Latreille, 1802

***Curculio venosus* Gravenhorst, 1807**

Fig. 10, 13

Material examined. 1 ex., Albania, Dibër County, Bulqizë Municipality, 1.5 km W Ostren I Madh vill., 41°25'34.01"N, 20°26'15.42"E, 1148 m, 12.V.2021, A.I. Gubin leg.

Remarks. The species is widely distributed in Europe and is also known from North Africa, Turkey, Transcaucasia and Afghanistan (Caldara, 2013; Alonso-Zarazaga et al., 2017). Examined specimen was collected in open montane woodland on *Quercus pubescens* Willd. (Fig. 13).

***Curculio villosus* Fabricius, 1781**

Figs 11-13

Material examined. 2 exs., Albania, Dibër County, Bulqizë Municipality, 1.5 km W Ostren I Madh vill., 41°25'34.01"N, 20°26'15.42"E, 1148 m, 12.V.2021, Yu.Ye. Skrylnyk leg.

Remarks. The species is widely distributed in Europe and is also known from North Africa, Turkey and Israel (Caldara, 2013; Alonso-Zarazaga et al., 2017). Examined specimens were collected in open montane woodland on *Quercus pubescens*. (Fig. 13).

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Figs 7-8. *Meloe (Taphromeloe) erythrocnemus* Pallas, 1782: 7 - imago, 8 - locality: Albania, Vlorë County, 4.5 km S Kaninë, Lungar Mts., 40°23'57.34"N, 19°31'5.06"E, 757 m., 05.05.2021.

Figs 9, 12. *Sphenoptera (Deudora) gemmata gemmata* A.G. Olivier, 1790: 9 - male, 12 - locality: Albania, Vlorë County, 3.5 km E Vagalat, 39°45'43.02"N, 20°9'39.46"E, 81 m, 06.05.2021.

Figs 10-11, 13. *Curculio* spp.: 10 - *Curculio venosus* Gravenhorst, 1807, imago, 11 - *Curculio villosus* Fabricius, 1781, imago, 13 - locality: Albania, Dibër County, Bulqizë Municipality, 1.5 km W Ostren I Madh vill., 41°25'34.01"N, 20°26'15.42"E, 1148 m., 12.05.2021.

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Three new *Litargus* Erichson, 1846 species (Coleoptera: Mycetophagidae) from Papua New Guinea and Fiji

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Key words: Coleoptera, Mycetophagidae, *Litargus*, taxonomy, new species, Fiji, Papua New Guinea.

Abstract. *Litargus (Litargosomus) papuanus* **sp. nov.** from Papua New Guinea, *Litargus (Litargosomus) buresweyrovae* **sp. nov.** and *Litargus (Litargosomus) fijiensis* **sp. nov.** both from Fiji Islands are described, illustrated and compared with a similar species, *Litargus (Litargosomus) vestitus* Sharp, 1879.

Introduction

The genus *Litargus* Erichson, 1846 can be divided into the following two subgenera: *Litargosomus* Motschulsky, 1858 and *Litargus* s. str. and currently contains 95 species worldwide (Háva 2022, 2025). From Papua New Guinea only one species, *Litargus (Litargosomus) vestitus* Sharp, 1879 is known; from the Fiji Islands only one species, *Litargus (Litargosomus) vestitus* Sharp, 1879 is known. Evenhuis & Ramsdale (2006, last revised in 2013) mentioned the species without detailed data.

The new species described here are from Fiji: Viti Levu and from Papua New Guinea: West New Britain Province.

Material and method

The type material is deposited in the following collections:

BMNH - British Museum Natural History London, England (D. Telnov);

JHAC - Jiří Háva, Private Entomological Laboratory & Collection, Únětice u Prahy, Prague-West, Czech Republic.

The size of the beetles or of their body parts can be useful in

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species recognition and thus, the following measurements were made:
total length (TL) - linear distance from anterior margin of head to apex of elytra.
elytral width (EW) - maximum linear transverse distance.

Results

Litargus (Litargosomus) papuanus sp. nov.

Figs 1-4

Description. Female. Body measurements TL 1.8 mm, EW 0.9 mm; oblong-oval, subparallel-sided; weakly convex dorsally, weakly glossy; black, covered with brown and yellow recumbent setation; elytra brown with yellowish patterns (Figs 1-3).

Head brown, with dense and coarse punctures; covered by yellow, recumbent setation; labrum brown; eyes prominent laterally in dorsal view, coarsely faceted and slightly emarginate near antennal insertions; antennae with 11 antennomeres, antennomeres light brown, antennal club with three antennomeres (Fig. 4); palpomeres light brown, apical maxillary palpomere large, cylindrical.

Pronotum brown with large dark brown spot, covered by light brown recumbent setation, convex dorsally, rugose, with large and dense punctures; widest posteriorly; anterior margin slightly arcuate; lateral sides roundly arcuate; basal margin sinuate, yellow, without short and circular grooves on subbasal parts.

Scutellum brown, triangular, with short recumbent light brown setation.

Elytra brown with yellowish patterns covered by yellow recumbent setation, brown patterns covered by brown setation, elongate, subparallel-sided, narrowed from apical 1/4 to apex (Figs 1-3). Epipleuron brown, covered with brown recumbent setation.

Meta - mesoventrite brown, with light brown recumbent setation, finely punctate.

Legs entirely light brown with light brown spines, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Tibiae with long brown spines apically.

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Abdominal visible ventrites brown, finely punctate, covered with light brown recumbent setation. Pygidium light brown, covered with light brown recumbent setation.

Male. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is very similar to *Litargus* (*Litargosomus*) *vestitus* Sharp, 1879, but differs from it by the black elytral cuticula, arrangement of yellowish elytral patterns and structure of antennae.

Type material. Holotype (♀) labelled: PAPUA N. GUINEA, W. New Britain Prov., Dani Oilpalm Res. Stn., 28.viii.1982, RNB. Prior. 1984.252 / No. 35669 on Oilpalm, C.I.E. A16759 / Pres by Comm Inst. Ent. B.M. 1985-1 / *Litargus* sp. det. R.B. Madge 1985, (BMNH). Paratypes (3 ♀♀): the same data s holotype, (2 BMNH, 1 JHAC); (1 ♀): PAPUA N. GUINEA, W. New Britain Prov., Dani Oilpalm Res. Stn. Hoskins / 1-3.xi.1980, on Oliplams K1662, C.I.E. A12863 / Pres by Comm Inst. Ent. B.M. 1985-1 / *Litargus* sp. det. R.B. Madge 1981, (specimen without abdomen), (BMNH).

Specimens of the presently described species are provided with red, printed labels with text as follows: „HOLOTYPE (or PARATYPE) *Litargus* (*Litargosomus*) *papuanus* sp. nov. Jiří Háva det. 2025”.

Etymology. Tomonymic, named for the Papua New Guinea, where the holotype was collected.

Litargus (*Litargosomus*) *buresweyrovae* sp. nov.

Figs 8-11

Description. Male. Body measurements TL 2.3 mm, EW 1.2 mm; oblong-oval, subparallel-sided; weakly convex dorsally, weakly glossy; black, covered with brown and yellow recumbent setation; elytra black with yellowish spots (Fig. 8).

Head black, with dense and coarse punctures; covered by brown, recumbent setation; labrum brown; eyes prominent laterally in dorsal view, coarsely faceted and slightly emarginate near antennal insertions; antennae with 11 antennomeres, antennomeres brown, antennal club with three antennomeres (Fig. 10); palpomeres dark brown, apical maxillary palpomere large, cylindrical.

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Pronotum brown, covered by brown recumbent setation, convex dorsally, rugose, with large and dense punctures; widest posteriorly; anterior margin slightly arcuate; lateral sides roundly arcuate; basal margin sinuate, without short and circular grooves on subbasal parts. Scutellum brown, triangular, with short recumbent brown setation.

Elytra brown with yellowish isolated spots covered by light brown recumbent setation forming longitudinal striation, brown patterns covered by brown setation, elongate, subparallel-sided, narrowed from apical 1/4 to apex, apical part without tip (Figs 8-9). Epipleuron brown, covered with brown recumbent setation.

Meta - mesoventrite brown, with light brown recumbent setation, finely punctate.

Legs brown with light brown spines, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Tibiae with long brown spines apically.

Abdominal visible ventrites brown, finely punctate, covered with light brown recumbent setation. Pygidium brown, covered with light brown recumbent setation.

Male genitalia (Fig. 11).

Female. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is similar to *Litargus (Litargosomus) vestitus* Sharp, 1879, but differs from it by the arrangement of yellowish elytral patterns and structure of antennae; from *Litargus (Litargosomus) fijiensis* **sp. nov.** differs by elytral setation (setation forming longitudinal striae), apex of elytron (Fig. 9), structure of antennae (Fig. 10) and male genitalia, parameres broad (Fig. 11).

Type material. Holotype (♂) labelled: Fiji, Viti Levu, Suva env., Colo I Suva, 18.05753S 178.46407E, 7.12.2024, L. Bureš Weyrová lgt., (JHAC).

Specimens of the presently described species are provided with red, printed labels with text as follows: „HOLOTYPE *Litargus (Litargosomus) buresweyrovae* sp. nov. Jiří Háva det. 2025”.

Etymology. Patronymic, dedicated to my friends and collectors of the new species, Lukáš Bureš and Dominika Weyrová (Brno, Czech Republic).

Figs 1-4. *Litargus (Litargosomus) papuanus* sp. nov.: 1. habitus, dorsal aspect of holotype; 2. habitus, dorso-lateral aspect of holotype; 3. habitus, dorsal aspect of paratype; 4. antenna;

Figs 5-7. *Litargus (Litargosomus) vestitus* Sharp, 1879: 5. habitus, dorsal aspect; 6. antenna; 7. male genitalia.

Figs 8-11. *Litargus (Litargosomus) buresweyrovae* sp. nov.: 8. habitus, dorsal aspect of holotype; 9. elytral apex; 10. antenna; 11. male genitalia.

Figs 12-15. *Litargus (Litargosomus) fijiensis* sp. nov.: 12. habitus, dorsal aspect of holotype; 13. elytral apex; 14. antenna; 15. male genitalia.

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***Litargus (Litargosomus) fijiensis* sp. nov.**

Figs. 12-15

Description. Male. Body measurements TL 2.2 mm, EW 1.0 mm; oblong-oval, subparallel-sided; weakly convex dorsally, weakly glossy; black, covered with brown and yellow recumbent setation; elytra black with yellowish spots (Fig. 12).

Head black, with dense and coarse punctures; covered by brown, recumbent setation; labrum brown; eyes prominent laterally in dorsal view, coarsely faceted and slightly emarginate near antennal insertions; antennae with 11 antennomeres, antennomeres brown, antennal club with three antennomeres (Fig. 14); palpomeres dark brown, apical maxillary palpomere large, cylindrical.

Pronotum brown, covered by brown recumbent setation, convex dorsally, rugose, with large and dense punctures; widest posteriorly; anterior margin slightly arcuate; lateral sides roundly arcuate; basal margin sinuate, without short and circular grooves on subbasal parts.

Scutellum brown, triangular, with short recumbent brown setation.

Elytra brown with yellowish isolated spots covered by light brown recumbent setation not forming striation, brown patterns covered by brown setation, elongate, subparallel-sided, narrowed from apical 1/4 to apex, apical part without tip (Figs 12-13). Epipleuron brown, covered with brown recumbent setation.

Meta - mesoventrite brown, with light brown recumbent setation, finely punctate.

Legs brown with light brown spines, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Tibiae with long brown spines apically.

Abdominal visible ventrites brown, finely punctate, covered with light brown recumbent setation. Pygidium brown, covered with light brown recumbent setation.

Male genitalia (Fig. 15).

Female. Unknown.

Type material. Holotype (♂) labelled: Fiji Is., Viti Levu, Navai, vii.2016, exEbay, (JHAC).

Specimens of the presently described species are provided

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with red, printed labels with text as follows: „HOLOTYPE *Litargus (Litargosomus) fijiensis* sp. nov. Jiří Háva det. 2025”.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is similar to *Litargus (Litargosomus) vestitus* Sharp, 1879, but differs from it by the arrangement of yellowish elytral patterns and structure of antennae; from *Litargus (Litargosomus) buresweyrovae* **sp. nov.** differs by elytral setation (setation not forming longitudinal striae), apex of elytron (Fig. 13), structure of antennae (Fig. 14) and male genitalia, parameres more narrow (Fig. 15).

Etymology. Tomonymic, named for the Fiji Islands, where the holotype was collected.

Acknowledgments. I am obliged very much to Dmitry Telnov (BMNH) for loaning me the interesting material, to Lukáš Bureš (Brno, Czech Republic) for donated me the interesting material and to Larry G. Bezark (California, U.S.A.) for comments and English revision of the manuscript.

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Description of a new species of *Crossotus* Audinet-Serville, 1835 from Saudi Arabia (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, new species, Saudi Arabia.

Abstract. *Crossotus asiricus* sp. nov. from Saudi Arabia. an unmistakable species with specific ecological requirements.

Introduction

There are 7 species plus 2 subspecies, of *Crossotus* Audinet-Serville, 1835 in the Arabian Peninsula, which can be divided into several groups based on their morphological similarity (Sudre *et al.* 2007). The new species described herein was compared with the following species: *Crossotus subocellatus subocellatus* (Fairmaire, 1886); *C. sublineatus* Gestro, 1892; *C. katbeh* Sama, 2000; *C. arabibus* Gahan, 1896; and *C. kadleci* Sama & Sudre, 2010.

Material and methods

Specimens of the new species were obtained by rearing larvae from wood imported from the type locality. The wood was placed in plastic boxes with perforated lids. The natural conditions of the region from which the wood came were simulated to preserve the larvae, especially temperature and humidity. The photographs of the specimens were taken with a Canon EOS 350D digital camera and a Sigma 105 mm macro lens. Composite images were created using the software Image Stacking Software Combine ZP. Microstructures of dissected parts were observed under the DNT DigiMicro Profi USB microscope. Each photograph was taken as several partially focused images and afterwards composed in the Helicon Focus 3.20.2 Pro software. The photographs were modified using Adobe Photoshop CC.

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Specimens examined, including type material, are deposited in the following collections:

LS - collection of Lukáš Skořepa (Dačice, Czech Republic)

NMPC - collection of National Museum (Prague, Czech Republic)

DS - collection of David Šanc (Plzeň, Czech Republic)

Results

Crossotus asiricus sp. nov.

Figs 1-4

Description. Habitus of male holotype is shown in Fig. 1, and that of female in Fig. 2. Body length ranges from 10 to 15 mm. Integument clack, grey pubescence is supplemented by a scattered mixture of white, golden brown, and black pubescence. Sides of prothorax with long, conical tubercle located about middle, and small blunt projection between anterior margin and central tubercle. Pronotum with slightly elevated gibbosities. Scutellum almost square, covered with dense pubescence, white on edges and golden brown or black on remaining surface. Elytra strongly arched, slightly narrowed towards apex; sparsely punctuated and densely covered mainly with grey pubescence, with longitudinal, irregular golden-brown pubescent lines and maculae, with arched, transverse dark-brown pubescent band on posterior half of elytra (Figs 3-4), irregular areas with whitish pubescence, and four basally located tufts of blackish setae on each elytron (two close to scutellum, one near humerus and the most prominent one located centrobasally). Antennae longer than body in males and slightly shorter than body in females; with dense, grey to ashy pubescence on the antennal segments, which becomes sparser towards the end of the segments, especially on the more distant ones.

Differential diagnosis. *Crossotus asiricus* sp. nov. must be compared with the species occurring in the same geographical region: *Crossotus subocellatus subocellatus*, *C. sublineatus*, *C. katbeh*, *C. arabibus*, and *C. kadleci*. Compared to these and other similar species native to Africa, *C. asiricus* differs by the distinct four tufts of black hairs on each elytron and by two distinct conical

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projections on each side of the pronotum. None of the species described in Sudre et al. (2007), who describes all known species of the genus *Crossotus*, correspond to the above-mentioned character. It also differs in size and relatively stable overall grey-gold coloration.

Type material. Holotype (♂) (Fig. 1): Saudi Arabia, (19°37'1.889"N, 41°54'49.997"E), Wadi Murharash, 15 km NW Sabt Al Alaya, 19.v.2024, ex. *Vachellia*, lar., L. Skořepa lgt. (NMPC); Paratypes: same data as holotype (4♂♂, 7♀♀) (LS); (4♂♂, 8♀♀) (DS); 1♂, Saudi Arabia, (20°10'21.235"N, 41°18'41.685"E), 4 km NE of Musaylah, 21.v.2024, ex. *Vachellia*, lar., L. Skořepa lgt. (LS); 1♂, 3 ♀♀, Saudi Arabia, (20°50'27.677"N, 40°46'19.201"E), 13 km NW Missan, ex. *Vachellia*, lar., L. Skořepa (LS).

Discussion. At first glance, the new species is clearly different from the known species of *Crossotus*, both from the Arabian Peninsula and from Africa. In body size, it is comparable to *C. strigifrons* (Fairmaire, 1886). This species is morphologically distinct; however, it can exhibit colour forms similar to *C. asiricus*.

Biology. Like most species of the genus, *C. asiricus* develops in the wood of trees from the genera *Vachellia*. Females lay eggs in smaller dead branches with a diameter of approximately 5 to 45 mm. The species was found mainly in locations above 1000 m a. s. l. in the Asir Mountains in Saudi Arabia.

Etymology. This species is named after the Asir Mountains in the southwestern Arabian Peninsula. The species name is therefore composed of the words Asir (mountain range) and icus (belonging to).

Acknowledgements. Sincere thanks are due to my friend D. Šanc (Plzeň) for his cooperation in the preparation of this study. Special thanks to David Navratil (Říkovice u Litomyšle) for preparing the photographs for this publication, and to Jiří Foit (Mendel University in Brno, Faculty of Forestry and Wood Technology, Czech Republic) for his indispensable assistance with the preparation of the manuscript.

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Figs 1-4. *Crossotus asiricus* sp. nov.: 1. Dorsal view habitus of male holotype; 2. Dorsal view of female paratype; 3. Lateral view habitus of male holotype; 4. Lateral view habitus of female paratype

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***Purpuricenus wachanrui anatolicus* ssp. nov. from Turkey and
Vadonia lazarevi sp. nov. from Greece (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae)**

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, new species, new subspecies, Palaearctic region.

Abstract. *Purpuricenus wachanrui anatolicus* **ssp. nov.** is described from Turkey (Adiyaman Province). *Vadonia lazarevi* **sp. nov.** is described from Greece (Crete).

***Purpuricenus wachanrui anatolicus* ssp. nov.**

Plate 1

Diagnosis. Body black, pronotum red, elytron black, but on its surface, there is a red spot, which occupies at least 1/3 of total area. Pronotum red, only the edges slightly black, sparsely dotted, the spaces between the dots are larger than the dots themselves. Pronotum very sparsely black-brown haired. Antennae black, thin and very short in relation to body length, compared to nominal species. And here is a very visible feature in males, where 3rd antennomeres is as long as the 5th antennomeres, where 4th and 6th antennomeres reach only 0.85% of length of 3rd and 5th antennomeres (plate 1). In addition, antennae in males shorter and their length exceeds end of elytron by only 2 antennomeres. Below we will compare this distinctive feature in nominal species *P. wachanrui wachanrui* in description. Body length of males and females: 13.0-14.0 mm.

Differential diagnosis: The new species *Purpuricenus wachanrui anatolicus* **ssp. nov.**, of genus *Purpuricenus* Dejean 1821, differs significantly from the nominal species *P. w. wachanrui* Levrat 1858. According to the original description, Levrat 1858, body

* The article is published in its original version without any changes.

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black, antennae black, slender, each antennomeres pointing upwards, slightly swollen. Antennae in males long, significantly exceeding the length of the elytron by at least 4 or more antennomeres. 3rd and 4th antennomeres equally long, in contrast, 5th and 6th antennomeres are 1.2 times longer than the previous two antennomeres (plate 1). These two very distinctive and visible characters that distinguish it from the new species. Head, short, black, finely pubescent, covered with black-brown hairs. Pronotum black, heavily dotted, spherical, full in middle, with shiny longitudinal lines, barely pronounced, which are a result of the absence of spines. Elytra one third wider than at the base of prothorax, slightly demarcated, almost parallel, up to 2/3 of the length black, covered with very strong punctation towards the anterior part and gradually weaker towards the end. Elytra decorated with a red spot. The new species *P. w. anatolicus* **ssp. nov.** has very distinctive features that distinguish it from all similar species of entire group, such as *P. w. wachanrui* Levrat 1858 from Iran, Iraq, Syria, Turkey, Cyprus, as well as *P. zarudnianus* Semenov 1908 from Iran, *P. nanus* Semenov 1907 from Iran, *P. robusticollis* Pic 1905 from Iran and *P. persicus* Vartanis 2023 from Iran. I have all of above-listed species in my collection.

Materials. Holotypes, male, Turkey, Adıyaman Prov., Kahta env., Nemrut Dagi Mt., 2-14.VI.1996, Petr Jelínek lgt. - collection of J. Vartanis; 7 Paratypes (collection of J. Vartanis); 2 males, 2 females, Turkey mer.or., Adıyamah-Kuyucak, 8.VI.1996, M. Snížek lgt.; 1 male, 1 female, Turkey, Adıyaman Prov., Nemrut Dagi Mt., Karadut env., 15.VI.2008, Pavel Jelínek lgt.; 1 female, Turkey, Adıyaman Prov., Kahta env., Nemrut Dagi Mt., 2-14.VI.1996, Petr Jelínek lgt.

Bionomy. Imagoes were found on flowers *Echinops* sp. (Asteracea).

Etymology. The new species was named after name of its area in eastern Turkey.

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Plate 1

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***Vadonia lazarevi* sp. nov.**

Plate 2, 3, 4

Diagnosis. Body, limbs, pronotum and antennae are black, elytra brownish-yellow. Antennae slender, reaching up to 2/3 of length of the elytron in males and up to 1/2 of length of the elytron in females. Limbs, short and strong, hind and middle femurs evenly covered with hair. Hind tibia with one spine. Feet of hind tarsi only partially brushed. Pronotum, black, spherical, very densely finely punctate, with a longitudinal smooth groove in middle, yellow-brown hairs, very dense and very prominent towards the outside. Elytron, brownish-yellow, each elytron with a smaller black spot in middle. The punctuation of elytron is very dense and fine, in 1/3 very distinct yellow-brown pubescence, in other 2/3 towards the apex glabrous, without pubescence. Elytra very short, stocky, strongly arched longitudinally, in the last fifth narrowing backwards. From scutellum along seam, slightly expanded indistinct black striations in males and more expanded in females. Body length in males: 13-14 mm, in females 13-15 mm.

Plate 2

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Differential diagnosis: I would like to analyze the large group of *Vadonia* species that occur in Greece. There are 18 species of the genus *Vadonia* in Greece and the new species *V. lazarevi* is 19th in order. Below I am inserting a map of all Greek species and species in blue frame fall into the group where males show only 1 spine on the hind tibia. There are 7 species in total with one spine. These 7 species are diametrically different from the new species *V. lazarevi*, they are larger, they belong to the group of large species, such as *V. bisignata bisignata*, *V. bisignata laurae*, *V. samosensis*, other species such as *V. dojranensis dojranensis*, *V. d. mahri* and *V. moesiaca* occur only in north of Greece and last species *V. monostigma* extends from Turkey, only to the north-eastern part of Greece. Moreover, none of these species shows a visible sign like new species *V. lazarevi*, where there is a black spot on the elytron, which extends from the scutellum and extends along elytron seam. Moreover, all penises in males were compared with all Greek species that I have in my collection. In addition to all the Greek species, I have the entire genus *Vadonia*.

Materials. Holotypes, male, Greece, Crete Isl., Idi Mt., Fourfouras, V.2024, Alexis Vartanis lgt. - collection of J. Vartanis; 15 Paratypes (collection of J. Vartanis); 11 males, 4 females, Greece, Crete Isl., Idi Mt., Fourfouras, V.2024, A. Vartanis lgt.

Bionomy. The adults were found on flowers of *Euphorbia* sp. The new subspecies is endemic of Crete and a single taxon of the genus in the island (plate 2).

Etymology. The new species is dedicated to a colleague and longhorn beetle specialist Maxim A. Lazarev (Free Economic Society of Russia, Moscow).

Acknowledgements. I would like to thanks Petr Jelínek (Czechia), Pavel Jelínek (Czechia), M. Snížek (Czechia), G. Mirotýs (Katerini, Greece), K. Stergiou (Thessaloniki, Greece), Alexis Vartanis (Thessaloniki, Greece), J. Resl (Dobruška, Czechia), J. Sobota (Hradec Králové, Czechia), M. Sláma (Praha, Czechia), J. Klícha (Čechtice, Czechia), for important data.

Vadonia genus, species occurring in Greece.

- 1) *V.albanica* Vartanis 2019 - HT,PT, GR,(Makedonia D,Ipiros). 2) *V.bisignata laurae* Pesarini & Sabbadini 2007 - GR,(Thessalia, E). 3) *V.bisignata bisignata* Brullé 1832 - GR,(Peloponissos, E). 4) *V.dojranensis dojranensis* Holzschuh 1984 - GR,(Makedonia kentriki). 5) *V.dojranensis mahri* Holzschuh 1985 - PT, GR,(Makedonia anatoliki,Thraki). 6) *V.gusmii* Pesarini & Sabbadini 2010 - GR,(Peloponissos, E). 7) *V.insidiosa* Holzschuh 1984 - GR,(Thessalia, E). 8) *V.klichai* Vartanis 2017 - HT,PT, GR,(Pindos Mt.,Ipiros, Corfu Isl., E). 9) *V.mainoldii* Pesarini & Sabbadini 2004 - GR,(Makedonia W., E). 10) *V.moesiaca* K.-J. Daniel 1891 - GR,(Makedonia W.,Ipiros). 11) *V.monostigma* Ganglbauer 1882 - GR,(Makedonia A.,Thraki) 12) *V.parnassensis* Pic 1925 - GR,(Sterea Ellada-Parnasos Mt., E). 13) *V.samosensis* Vartanis 2016 - HT,PT - GR,(Samos Isl., E). 14) *V.unipunctata dalmatina* Müller 1907 - GR,(Makedonia). 15) *V.unipunctata ikariaensis* Danilevsky & Vartanis 2015 - HT,PT, - GR,(Ikaria Isl., E). 16) *V.unipunctata makedonica* Holzschuh 1989 - PT, GR,(Makedonia anatoliki,kentriki,Thraki, E). 17) *V.unipunctata ohridensis* Holzschuh 1987 - PT, GR,(Makedonia W.,Ipiros). 18) *V.unipunctata unipunctata* Fabricius 1787 - GR,(Olympos Mt.). 19) *Vadonia lazarevi* Vartanis 2026 - HT,PT, - GR,(Creta Isl., E). HT-Holotypus, PT-Paratypus E - Endemic species of Greece.

Plate 3

Species in the blue box are males that have only 1 spine on the hind tibia, compared to species not in the blue box, where males have 2 spines on the hind tibia.

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Elytra entirely yellow, the tips not blackened, as in all other species below. The new species is endemic to the island of Crete. This is a smaller species, 13-14mm.	Elytra entirely yellow, the tips not blackened, as in all other species below. In some specimens a black spot extends from the scutellum, along the seam, to the middle of the elytron.	Elytra yellow, but at the end of the tips they are always blackened, both in males and females. This is a large species, probably one of the largest in the entire genus, where individuals exceed 20 mm. It is an endemic species for the Peloponnese peninsula.	Elytra yellow, but at the end of the tips they are always blackened, both in males and females. This is a large species, where individuals reach 17-19mm. The destination of occurrence is in central Greece, in the region of Thessaly, it is not widespread elsewhere.	Elytra yellow, but at the end of the tips they are always blackened, both in males and females. This is a large species, the size can exceed 20 mm. The photo shows the Holotype . This is an endemic species of the island of Samos.
<i>Vadonia lazarevi sp.n.</i> Creta Isl.	<i>Vadonia lazarevi sp.n.</i> Creta Isl.	<i>V.bisignata bisignata</i> Peloponnissos	<i>V.bisignata laurae</i> Central Greece	<i>Vadonia samosensis</i> Samos Isl.
Elytra yellow, but at the end of the tips they are always blackened, both in males and females. This is a large species, the size can reach 16-18 mm. Occurrence only in eastern Macedonia in northern Greece. This is a Paratypus , from the collection of the Vienna Museum.	Elytra yellow, but at the end of the tips they are always blackened, both in males and females. It is a medium-sized species, around 13-14 mm. Destination of occurrence in Greece only in the north, throughout the region of Macedonia.	Elytra yellow, but at the end of the tips they are always blackened, both in males and females. It is a medium-sized species, around 14-16mm. The destination of occurrence in Greece is very limited, only in central Macedonia, very rarely.	Elytra yellow, but at the end of the tips they are always blackened, both in males and females. It is a medium-sized species, around 14-16mm. Destination of occurrence in Greece, mainly in the eastern part of Macedonia and Thrace, much more abundant than the previous species.	Elytra completely black, this is a rare aberration of the species. In the photo Paratypus from my collection. Destination of occurrence in Greece, in the eastern region of Macedonia and Thrace.
<i>Vadonia monostigma</i> Macedonia E	<i>Vadonia moesiaca</i> Macedonia	<i>V.dojran.dojranensis</i> Macedonia C	<i>V.dojranensis mahri</i> Macedonia E	<i>V.dojranensis mahri</i> Macedonia E

Plate 4

The 8 species below, including the new species *Vadonia lazarevi* from island Crete, have only (1 spine) on hind tibia in males, whole other species in Greece have (2 spines). Below I have shown a comparison of elytron with each other, in addition 3 species are Holotypus and Paratypus from my collection and 1 specimen from Vienna Museum.

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**Commentary on *Geonigidius* Xin, Gong, Zhong & Qi, 2025,
“the first brachypterous stag beetle in Eurasia”, with proposition
of synonymy with *Nigidius* Macleay, 1819**

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Key words: Coleoptera, Lucanidae, taxonomy, new synonym, new combination.

Abstract. *Nigidius* Macleay, 1819 = *Geonigidius* Xin, Gong, Zhong & Qi, 2025, **syn. n.**, and *Nigidius sinensis* (Xin, Gong, Zhong & Qi, 2025), **comb. n.**

On 11 December 2025 an article entitled “The first discovery of brachypterous stag beetle in Eurasia: A remarkable new genus and species of the tribe Figulini Burmeister, 1847 (Coleoptera: Lucanidae: Lucaninae) from southwestern China” was published online in *Zootaxa*. The paper described an impressive and sensational new species, *Geonigidius sinensis* Xin, Gong, Zhong & Qi, 2025, which was assigned to the newly erected genus *Geonigidius* Xin, Gong, Zhong & Qi, 2025.

The authors repeatedly asserted that brachyptery constitutes a first record for Eurasian Lucanidae: in Abstract “Despite centuries of active research on Eurasian Lucanidae, the absence of species with vestigial hindwings has remained a significant knowledge gap.”,

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on page 531 “Notably, no such case had been discovered in continental Eurasia before this study, ...”, and on page 546 “this trait remains notably unreported from Eurasian species.” The unpublished data of these authors, however, appear to be incomplete. The condition of atrophied hindwings has previously been observed or inferred in certain Eurasian lucanid lineages, as listed below.

***Aegus hikidai* Araya, 1994**

Araya, 1994: title “Discovery of a flightless *Aegus* (Coleoptera, Lucanidae) in Borneo”, 271 “... a female of the genus *Aegus* with atrophied wings ...”, 273 “Hindwings (Fig. 2) very short and atrophied, 0.52 times the elytral length (about 3.2 mm in length);”, 278 “Atrophied wings and firmly interlocked elytra are also its unique characteristics shared by no other species in the genus.”, 278 “... the atrophied wings of *A. hikidai* are very short (0.52 times the elytral length).”

Fujita 2010: 331 “後翅が退化した特異なネプトクワガタ。 [A peculiar *Aegus* whose hindwings are reduced.]”.

***Aegus inaharai* Fujita, 2010**

Fujita, 2010: 330 “次種のムルハネナシネプトと同様に後翅が退化した種と思われる, [Like the following species *Aegus hikidai*, this species is thought to have atrophied hindwings.]”.

***Nigidius sticheri* Okuda et Fukinuki, 2000**

Fujita 2010: 408 “小さく、基方が狭まった上翅の形態から、本種は後翅が退化しているか、ほとんど飛翔しない種の可能性がある。 [Based on the small, basally narrowed shape of the elytra, this species likely has atrophied hindwings or is a species that rarely flies.]”.

In addition, the justification offered for erection of the genus *Geonigidius* is insufficiently robust. The authors placed primary emphasis on brachyptery, treating it as a decisive generic character; for example they stated on page 546 that “As brachyptery generally remains stable within genera, it serves as a reliable generic-level character.” This reliance is misplaced. The suite of characters that

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distinguish *G. sinensis* from members of *Nigidius*, including the four characters in the identification key and the nine diagnostic differences listed in the Diagnosis, are best interpreted as autapomorphies of a specialised species rather than as synapomorphies that would justify recognition of a separate genus. Erecting a monotypic genus on the basis of such derived, apparently species-level modifications is arbitrary and tenuous. On the basis of the foregoing considerations, the following new subjective synonymy is proposed: *Nigidius* Macleay, 1819 = *Geonigidius* Xin, Gong, Zhong & Qi, 2025, **syn. n.** The type species is transferred accordingly as *Nigidius sinensis* (Xin, Gong, Zhong & Qi, 2025), **comb. n.**

This proposal is advanced to encourage further critical assessment of generic limits within the Figulini and to promote careful evaluation of character polarity before the establishment of new genera.

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